

THE LINK OF MEDICINE AND PHILOSOPHY

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Annotation: The article describes the interrelationships of medical and philosophical sciences, as well as the results of theoretical, practical ideas, comments and research in the field of medical philosophy. An analysis of philosophical approaches to medicine is given.

Keywords: ontological, epistemological, ethical, character, client, ethics, norm, pathology, diagnosis, prevention.

Relevance: the philosophy of Medicine is a branch of the philosophy of science that deals with ontological, gnoseological and moral issues in the field of medicine as a separate field of theoretical and practical activity of man. The philosophy of Medicine is a system of generalizing reasoning and a set of humanitarian knowledge, as a subject and method of Medicine, the role of medicine among other sciences and spheres of human activity, its cognitive and social role in modern society, an integral system of Natural Science. One of the most important sections of the philosophy of Medicine and bioethics is medical ethics, which prioritizes the issues of interaction between the doctor and the patient.

The purpose of the study: medicine as a science is “a specific unit of cognitive and value forms of reflection and transformative activity”. It gathers knowledge about health and illness, treatment and Prevention, norms and pathology, the impact of natural, social and spiritual factors on a person. Medicine has all the signs of a certain field of knowledge. In addition to its subject matter, it has its own methods of study and scope of practical application, namely: prevention and treatment of diseases, as well as strengthening health. Through the subject of the study, medicine is associated with social sciences. Fields of medicine, such as Labor hygiene, nutrition, housing and recreation, are closely related to a number of Social Sciences. Since Medicine studies biological processes in the human body, it is close to such Sciences as biophysics, biochemistry, genetics, physiology, Embryology, anthropology, microbiology.

Material and methods: several centuries ago there was a knowledge based on a philosophical approach to medical science. This knowledge was reached through the works of Ibn Sina and legends about him. There are legends about the various methods (treatment with herbs, mental exposure) that Ibn Sina used to treat patients with severe condition. In fact, these are facts that have become legends. Ibn Sina found out that the causes of the occurrence of diseases are environmental, lifestyle and mental states, and noted that in the treatment and Prevention of the disease, initially, it is necessary to eliminate these situations positively. This opinion he has also proved through experience. Ibn Sina kept one sheep in normal conditions, and the other in a cage, and fed the elixir the same. Around the sheep in the cage, the wolf wandered. After a day or two, the sheep in the cage, wandering around by the Wolf, will not eat food and will die of exhaustion. Ibn Sina concluded that the death of the sheep was caused by mental stress and, as a result, the depletion of the organism. Ibn Sina graduated also many brochures devoted to the problems of deontology. He argues that it is necessary to pay attention to his person in the treatment of the expression "cure the patient, not the disease". Medical science has historically always included a certain philosophical component, which requires a dialectical approach to the study of the human body in normal and pathological conditions. Egyptian medicine became the basis for understanding the problems of creating a healthy lifestyle for people.

Conclusion and discussion: despite the different spheres of activity and different ways of searching for truth, their ambivalence also solves the same problem - the survival of mankind, the self-determination of man as a natural and cultural being, makes it morally meaningful. Medicine almost always has problems with which philosophy can answer. The philosophy of Medicine and pharmacology rivojlan develops and improves dialectical thinkingtiradi. Philosophical culture allows doctors to overcome the monotony in the approach to the problems studied in conditions of high specialized scientific and practical activity.

Conclusion

In conclusion, I can say that in the treatment of the body there are not enough pharmacological agents. In the Endi queue, it is also necessary to include philosophical psychological views, which are rich in new content in medicine. From the point of view of my many years of scientific research and practical and theoretical knowledge I have studied, I can say that the sincere attitude of a person to a person, that is, human human relations, is valued at a higher value

than human technical relations. Today, we can not achieve success in clinical trials without the direct use of human relations.

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